

Signs of Possible High-Temperature Superconductivity in Graphite Intercalated with Calcium-Ammonia Solutions

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ABSTRACT

We report experimental results indicating possible superconductivity with high critical temperatures (T_c) at atmospheric pressure in graphite intercalation compounds. In this study, we focus on the graphite-ammonia-calcium system, where we first discovered high-temperature anomalies in magnetization, trapped magnetic flux, and electrical resistance measurements at temperatures ranging from 200 K to 262 K. Ammonia readily dissolves calcium at temperatures well below its melting point and facilitate delivery of the metal into graphite. Our results and analyses suggest that the observed transitions originate from local superconductivity rather than intrinsic magnetic properties of the intercalated graphite, which may be an alternative explanation. Accordingly, we propose and intend to pursue further investigations to test and confirm the nature of the observed high-temperature transitions.

INTRODUCTION

Superconductivity is remarkable property of a material to conduct electrical current without resistance. First discovered in pure mercury by Onnes in 1911¹, this property was long considered an exclusively low-temperature phenomenon. A paradigm shift occurred only at the end of the 1980s, when Bednorz and Müller discovered a new family of cuprate superconductors². Subsequent extensive screening of various cuprate compounds for high-temperature superconductivity led to a maximum T_c of approximately 133 K at ambient pressure³ and 164 K under high pressure⁴. However, further progress has been hindered, in part due to the absence of a comprehensive theory for unconventional superconductivity. Since then, no superconductor with a higher T_c at ambient pressure has been discovered.

The breakthrough came with the discovery of superconductivity in H_3S at megabar pressures, exhibiting a T_c of 203 K⁵. This marked a revolutionary path toward superconductors operating at room temperatures. Soon after, even higher T_c s were achieved in metal superhydrides, e.g., $T_c \approx 243$ K in YH_9 ^{6,7} and $T_c \approx 250$ K in LaH_{10} ^{8,9}. Theoretical calculations predict that T_c s close to or even exceeding room temperature are possible in various hydrogen-rich systems under extreme pressures^{10,11}.

Although such highly compressed hydrides are only stable at multimegabar pressures – far beyond current technological applications – they unequivocally demonstrate that superconductivity is not fundamentally limited to low temperatures. Materials with high-frequency phonon spectra and strong electron-phonon coupling can, in principle, exhibit high T_c values. These discoveries also provide good example of the synergy between experiment and theory utilizing modern crystal structure prediction methods¹².

In addition to hydrides, compounds consisting of other light elements (e.g. B, C, N *etc.*)^{13,14} also have the potential to exhibit high-temperature conventional superconductivity^{15,16}. In particular, carbon-based materials have long been explored as promising candidates for high- T_c superconductors¹⁷. Their unique electronic structures – such as delocalized π -electron systems and low-dimensional frameworks – can enhance electron pairing and electron-phonon interactions. The low atomic mass of

carbon contributes to higher vibrational frequencies, which further strengthen these interactions. Moreover, the tuneable electronic properties of carbon materials make it possible to investigate a wide range of superconducting phases, including those involving unconventional mechanisms.

For example, substituting a small fraction of carbon atoms with boron in the diamond lattice induces metallic behavior and superconductivity with a T_c near 4 K¹⁸. Heavily doped amorphous Q-carbon (with ~30% boron) becomes superconducting with a T_c as high as 55 K¹⁹. Doping other carbon allotropes can also lead to superconductivity with the highest $T_c \approx 33$ K reported for Cs₂RbC₆₀²⁰.

Similarly, appropriate intercalation of graphite – for instance, with alkali or alkaline-earth metals – can also lead to superconductivity²¹. The concept of charge transfer from the intercalant to the low dimensional system of graphene sheets in graphite, resulting in the emergence of superconductivity, has been exploited for over 50 years^{22,23}. However, the highest T_c reported in such systems, also known as graphite intercalation compounds, is approximately 11.5 K, observed in CaC₆^{24,25} and Ca₂Li₃C₆²⁶ at atmospheric pressure, and 15.1 K at 7.5 GPa in CaC₆²⁷. These materials are generally described by conventional BCS theory rather than requiring exotic electronic mechanisms^{28,29}.

Systematically exploring the possibility of high-temperature superconductivity in carbon-based systems, we have discovered new materials exhibiting pronounced transitions at high temperatures and atmospheric pressure. Here, we report experimental evidence suggesting the emergence of possible high-temperature superconductivity in graphite intercalated by calcium-ammonia solutions.

RESULTS

Experimental signature of apparent transitions in novel graphite intercalation compounds which may have superconducting origin is provided by independent and complementary magnetization and electrical resistance measurements. The observed effects agree with hallmarks of type II superconductivity, including: 1) diamagnetic screening and magnetic field expulsion (Meissner effect); 2) the characteristic magnetization behaviour upon sweeping applied magnetic fields; 3) magnetic flux trapping with characteristic differences between zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) modes; 4) drop in electrical resistance below T_c .

1. Screening and expulsion of applied magnetic fields.

The various samples synthesized via intercalation of graphite with liquid calcium–ammonia solutions exhibit pronounced steps in the $m(T)$ magnetization measurements, observed in the temperature range of approximately 230–260 K (see Fig. 1). This behaviour suggests that below these temperatures the applied magnetic field is effectively screened by the sample interior, indicating a diamagnetic nature of the low-temperature state. These steps in the $m(T)$ curves are pronounced in the ZFC measurements, while their magnitudes are significantly reduced in the FC measurements.

A clear manifestation of magnetic field expulsion upon FC mode – consistent with the Meissner effect – is evident in Sample I (see Fig.1 a). The change in magnetic moment at the transition, Δm , measured in the FC mode is approximately 7% of Δm observed in the ZFC mode. The substantial difference between the change in magnetic moment in the FC and ZFC measurements is characteristic of type II superconductors, where partial magnetic field penetration occurs in the mixed state in the form of vortices. The reduced or negligible Δm values in FC $m(T)$ curves may indicate strong vortex pinning in samples.

Although the conditions of the intercalation process (temperature, duration, and concentration of metal-ammonia solutions) were kept for Samples I, II and III the same, the resulting samples exhibit significant variation in T_c in $m(T)$ measurements – up to approximately 30 K. This variation may stem from differences in the degree of intercalation of graphite and/or the ammonia-to-calcium ratio retained

in the graphite matrix after the removal of excess ammonia. These findings suggest that T_c could potentially be further enhanced by optimizing the synthesis parameters.

Figure 1. Magnetization $m(T)$ measurements of graphite samples intercalated with calcium–ammonia solutions. a) – c) ZFC and FC $m(T)$ data for three samples (Sample I, II, and III), demonstrating step-like transitions with T_c s ranging from approximately 230 K to 260 K. A zoomed-in view of the $m(T)$ curve for Sample I measured under FC protocol (highlighting the possible Meissner effect) is shown at the top of panel a. d), e) Photographs of graphite samples intercalated with saturated Ca–NH₃ solutions. The images show the intercalated samples just after the synthesis cut along the carbon layers.

2. Magnetization $m(H)$ measurements.

We also performed $m(H)$ magnetization measurements on samples cooled to temperatures below the transitions observed in the $m(T)$ curves to investigate their response to applied magnetic fields. The measured data for Sample I and Sample IV are summarized in Fig. 2 and exhibit three characteristic features consistent with type II superconductivity: (i) an initial linear trend in the virgin $m(H)$ curve, indicating full magnetic field screening (consistent with the Meissner state); (ii) a subsequent deviation from linearity, reflecting partial penetration of magnetic flux into the sample (indicating a transition to the mixed state); (iii) the appearance of hysteretic loops upon sweeping the magnetic field, signifying magnetic flux trapping.

It should be noted that the measured $m(H)$ curves are affected by different magnetic background properties – paramagnetic in Sample I and diamagnetic in Sample IV. The background magnetization most likely originates from other phases present in the samples, such as unreacted graphite or excess metal-ammonia solution. Indeed, independent magnetization measurements confirmed a paramagnetic response from the saturated Ca-ammonia solutions and the diamagnetic response from the pristine graphite (see Supplementary Fig. S1). Crucially, neither pristine graphite nor metal-ammonia solutions exhibit step-like transitions in the $m(T)$ measurements and thus cannot account for the transitions observed in the synthesized graphite intercalation compounds.

From the initial part of the $m(H)$ curves, we estimated the penetration field (H_p) – the applied field at which magnetic flux begins to penetrate the sample – as the point where the virgin $m(H)$ curve deviates from linearity. The estimated values are $\mu_0 H_p \approx 12$ mT for sample I at $T = 30$ K, and $\mu_0 H_p \approx 18$ mT for sample IV at $T = 10.2$ K.

Figure 2. Magnetization $m(H)$ measurements of graphite samples intercalated with calcium–ammonia solutions. a), b) $m(H)$ data for Sample I at $T = 30$ K and Sample IV at $T = 10.2$ K, showing the hysteretic loops upon sweeping applied magnetic fields in the range from -1 T to $+2.5$ T for Sample I and from -0.3 T to $+0.3$ T for Sample IV. For clarity, only the range of -0.1 T $< \mu_0 H_{appl} < +0.1$ T is shown to highlight the hysteretic behavior. The magnetic field was applied perpendicular to the carbon layers. Magenta circles indicate the initial virgin magnetization curves, while grey circles represent hysteresis loops. Insets show enlarged views of the data highlighting the deviation of the virgin curves from the initial linear trend. The green lines are guides for the eye.

3. Magnetic flux trapping.

In addition to conventional $m(T)$ and $m(H)$ magnetization measurements, we investigated magnetic flux trapping – another hallmark of type II superconductivity^{30,31}. The trapped flux method has recently proven effective for probing superconductivity and estimating superconducting parameters in high- T_c hydrogen-rich compounds under high pressure³², as well as in other superconductors at ambient pressure^{33,34}.

Flux trapping arises from the persistence of superconducting currents after the sample has been exposed to a magnetic field. The resulting positive induced magnetic moment, m_{trap} , decreases with increasing temperature due to the reduction in critical current and thermally activated flux creep, and disappears entirely at the superconducting-to-normal state transition temperature, T_c . Fig. 3 shows m_{trap} data for Sample V, revealing clear steps near 230 K, which indicate the loss of trapped flux. The transition temperature observed in flux-trapping measurements agree well with those from conventional $m(T)$ magnetization data (see Fig. 3b).

Importantly, the characteristic behaviour of m_{trap} generated under ZFC and FC modes provides further evidence for type II superconductivity in the novel graphite intercalation compounds. In the ZFC mode, the sample is cooled from $T > T_c$ to a target temperature $T_M < T_c$ in zero magnetic field. When a magnetic field H_M is applied at T_M and then removed, magnetic flux is excluded in the Meissner state unless H_M exceeds the penetration field H_p . In contrast, in the FC mode, when the sample is cooled in the presence of H_M , the magnetic penetrates in the sample in the normal state and becomes trapped below T_c due to vortex pinning, even if $H_M < H_p$. As a result, the trapped magnetic moment is systematically higher in the FC mode than in the ZFC mode at the same field strength, until saturation is reached (see method details in Refs.³²).

In Sample V, m_{trap} generated under the FC mode at $\mu_0 H_M = 16$ mT (close to the estimated $\mu_0 H_p$ values from $m(H)$ data) is almost an order of magnitude larger than that obtained in ZFC mode. At $\mu_0 H_M = 80$ mT, the difference is smaller, with $m_{\text{trap}}(\text{FC})$ approximately twice that of $m_{\text{trap}}(\text{ZFC})$. Further increasing $\mu_0 H_M$ to 2 T results in $m_{\text{trap}}(\text{ZFC})$ values comparable to $m_{\text{trap}}(\text{FC}, \mu_0 H_M = 80$ mT), indicating saturation of trapped flux. This suggests that the full penetration field H^* at which the magnetic flux penetrates the entire sample lies in the vicinity of 80 mT.

Figure 3. Trapping of magnetic flux below T_c in graphite samples intercalated with calcium–ammonia solution. **a)** Temperature dependence of the induced magnetic moment in Sample V. Magnetic flux trapping was performed at the magnetization temperature $T_M = 3.8$ K and various applied magnetic fields: $\mu_0 H_M = 16$ mT and 80 mT under FC mode (open circles), and $\mu_0 H_M = 16$ mT, 80 mT, and 2 T under ZFC mode (filled circles). The magnetic field was applied perpendicular to the carbon layers in the sample. Black arrows indicate the temperature sweep direction. Data obtained during reverse cooling show a temperature-independent background after release of trapped flux in the warming cycle. **b)** Conventional $m(T)$ magnetization measurements for Sample V at $\mu_0 H_{\text{appl}} = 6$ mT (black circles) and $\mu_0 H_{\text{appl}} = 18$ mT (red circles), demonstrating clear transition in ZFC curve at approximately 230 K.

4. Four-probe electrical resistance measurements.

Electrical transport measurements provide an independent and complementary approach to magnetization techniques for elucidating the origin of the observed transitions in graphite samples intercalated with Ca–NH₃ solutions. Electrical resistance decreases sharply at T_c and becomes temperature-independent upon further cooling (see Fig. 4). Such behaviour of $R(T)$ may also indicate a superconducting transition, where the sudden drop in $R(T)$ signals the onset of a zero-resistance state. The observed changes in $R(T)$ are reproducible upon warming-cooling cycles.

Importantly, we observed an increase in transition temperature during successive cooling–warming cycles (see magenta curve in Fig. 4a and salmon curve in Fig. 4b). The lower T_c s recorded in the first cycle are likely due to a higher ammonia content in the graphite intercalation compounds. The intercalated samples were lifted from the metal-ammonia solution using a holder with four-probe electrical contacts after the synthesis and subsequent electrical measurements were performed on cooling. This may suggest that variation in the concentration of intercalated Ca and ammonia could influence T_c values, potentially explaining the differences observed among various samples of the graphite–calcium–ammonia system (see Fig.1 and Fig. 4).

The onset of resistive transitions in intercalated graphite samples was observed in the temperature range of approximately 190–260 K. These values are in good agreement with the onset temperatures observed in independent magnetization measurements ($T_c \approx 230$ –260 K).

Figure 4. Four-probe electrical transport measurements of graphite samples intercalated with calcium-ammonia solutions. a), b) In-situ temperature-dependent four-probe electrical resistance measurements of Sample VI and Sample VII. Circles of different colors represent data from successive warming-cooling cycles. Open circles correspond to cooling, while filled circles correspond to warming.

DISCUSSIONS

In the present study we synthesized and investigated several dozens of samples intercalated with Ca-NH₃ solutions. Pronounced transitions were detected in approximately 50% of the samples, likely due to the rapid degradation of the materials during handling, caused by the high reactivity of both metal-ammonia solutions and the intercalation products. Various magnetization and electrical resistance measurements support the superconducting origin of the observed transitions, rather than an alternative mechanism. The experimental results demonstrate signatures of magnetic field screening and expulsion, flux trapping, and a drop in electrical resistance below T_c . Crucially, these high-temperature features are observed only in the intercalated graphite samples, not in pristine graphite or calcium-ammonia solutions (see Supplementary Figure S1).

A key challenge in studying these materials is a low volume fraction of the phase responsible for high- T_c transitions. Using a known Pb superconductor of equal size as a reference, we estimated that the volume fraction in the intercalated graphite samples does not exceed 0.1% of the bulk product (see companion study³⁵). This estimate assumes a uniform distribution of the phase and does not account for the demagnetization factor. The low volume fraction makes further structural characterization of the high- T_c phase particularly challenging.

Attempts to increase this fraction by extending the intercalation time were unsuccessful. Graphite samples intercalated with Ca-ammonia solutions for one week showed no significant increase in Δm values observed in $m(T)$ measurements. Similarly, repeated intercalation cycles did not yield higher fractions of the high- T_c phase (see Supplementary Fig. S2).

Interestingly, different synthetic routes for graphite intercalation – using either Ca-NH₃ solutions (present study) or Li-based metal alloys (companion study³⁵) – resulted in materials with similarly high T_c values. This suggests that NH₃ in metal-ammonia solutions and Li in the alloy-based

approach³⁵ primarily act as solvents and carriers for intercalating metals. Both NH₃ and Li readily dissolve Ca metal at temperatures well below the melting point of Ca and facilitate intercalation of Ca into the graphite lattice. Doping of graphite by the appropriate element appears to be the key factor in the emergence of possible superconductivity in these compounds. However, we do not rule out the possibility that NH₃ (or Li) may also induce secondary beneficial effects, such as modifications to interlayer spacing between graphene sheets, the formation of packing faults, or other structural rearrangements.

An important question is whether even higher T_c values of the observed transitions can be achieved in these materials. Our current results already show a significant increase in T_c : the first observed transition at approximately 230 K in graphite samples intercalated with Ca–NH₃ solutions was followed by T_c values up to ≈ 350 K in samples intercalated with ternary Li–Ca–Sr alloys³⁵. Further enhancement of T_c may be possible by tuning the intercalation conditions, modifying the host matrix, varying the intercalants, or applying external pressure. Our ongoing experiments suggests that possible high- T_c superconductivity in graphite intercalation compounds is not limited to Ca-containing systems³⁵.

At present, the mechanism underlying the possible high-temperature superconductivity in these novel graphite-based materials remains unclear. One plausible scenario involves the formation of a specific crystal phase, e.g., characterized by a particular staging (intercalated layers alter with non-intercalated graphene layers) and concentration of the doping element, which provides optimal charge transfer to the graphite lattice. However, the observation of similarly low superconducting fractions across samples with different intercalation times and different synthesis methods does not support this hypothesis.

An alternative explanation involves the presence of flat bands³⁶ at the Fermi level realized at structural defects within the graphite host matrix³⁷⁻³⁹. Theoretical studies suggest that interfaces between slightly twisted graphite regions (e.g., between the rhombohedral and Bernal phases³⁶) can support topologically protected surface states with flat bands at the Fermi level, which may favor high T_c superconductivity³⁷. Stacking faults have also been proposed as a source of flat bands³⁶, and appropriate doping of such regions could lead to high electronic density of states and enhanced electron pairing interactions. The small superconducting fractions observed in various samples, and the fact that different synthetic routes yield similarly high T_c values, are consistent with this model.

In summary, we report first observations of possible high-temperature superconductivity in graphite intercalation compounds. Further experimental and theoretical studies are required to clarify the nature of the observed effects, determine the structure of the possible superconducting phase, and uncover the mechanism behind the extraordinary high T_c values in these materials.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the present study we used highly oriented pyrolytic graphite, HOPG (purity 99.99%, Magnametals) as a main source of graphite for the reproducible synthesis of superconducting samples. In separate experiments we also used another source of graphite – expanded graphite sheets SGL (purity > 99.85%, SGL CARBON GmbH) – and obtained similar transition in $m(T)$ measurements.

Prior intercalation of samples by metal–ammonia solutions the graphite was annealed at $T = 723$ K in Ar–H₂ flow for 2 hours to remove absorbed gases and water from the interior. Untreated graphite samples were also used in our experiments, however the reproducibility rate of products exhibiting high- T_c transitions was lower.

For intercalation reactions the following reactants were used: NH₃ (99.999%, Westfalen), Ca (99.5%, redistilled, Alfa Aesar), anhydrous silicone oil and kerosene both dried with metallic sodium in Ar atmosphere.

In the present study we performed intercalation of graphite samples with metal-ammonia solutions. This technique provides good dissolution of the doping metal at temperatures significantly lower than its melting point and effective delivery of the metal into the graphite matrix.

Intercalation of graphite samples with calcium–ammonia solutions.

Intercalation of graphite samples with calcium–ammonia solutions was conducted using 25-ml-volume Schlenk flasks and 21-ml-volume test-tubes. All glassware was meticulously cleaned, including cleaning in a base bath (potassium hydroxide / isopropanol), and in a 3:1 mixture of concentrated HCl and HNO₃ acids, followed by thorough rinsing by deionized water. The glassware was then dried at 420 K for 24 hours to remove adsorbed water, preventing the decomposition of metal-ammonia solutions.

For a typical synthesis, a bulk piece of HOPG (SGL) and weighed pieces of metallic Ca were transferred into the glassware, which was then sealed under an argon atmosphere in a glovebox (MBraun) with residual O₂ and H₂O levels below 0.1 ppm. The glassware containing the reactants was connected to a condensation setup and evacuated to approximately 10⁻⁵ bar. The entire condensation line was purged with gaseous NH₃ and vacuumed multiple times.

The condensation of liquid ammonia and the synthesis were done in glassware at approximately 200 K using a dry ice–ethanol bath. Some syntheses were done using liquid N₂–ethanol base to reach approximately 180 K. Upon condensation, NH₃ immediately reacted with Ca pieces forming intensely colored solutions. During the preparation of Ca–NH₃ solutions, graphite samples were either immersed in the reaction liquid or kept above it using a special manipulator. In the second case, graphite samples were lowered into the prepared Ca–NH₃ solutions after condensation of NH₃. The typical intercalation process was carried out at 200 K for 30-60 minutes. The concentration of Ca in metal–ammonia solutions varied from approximately 5 mol% (dark blue solutions) to approximately 15 mol% in saturated solutions with excess metal phase (bronze solutions with a metallic luster).

After the intercalation reaction, the following protocol was applied:

1. *Removal of excess NH₃*: The reaction mixture with the intercalated graphite sample was pumped out at $T \approx 200$ K for approximately 0.2–1 hour until the metal–ammonia solutions solidified.
2. *Warming*: The mixture was warmed to room temperature while continuing to pump for approximately 5–20 minutes.
3. *Atmosphere restoration*: The pump was turned off, and the glassware was filled with helium gas (99.999% Westfalen) to approximately 1 bar.
4. *Protection*: Anhydrous kerosene or silicone oil was added in the reaction flask to protect the highly reactive products from ambient air.
5. *Extraction*: The intercalated graphite samples were separated from the solidified metal–ammonia solution.

In particular, Sample I was prepared by intercalating graphite with saturated Ca–NH₃ solution (excess Ca, gold color with metallic luster) at temperatures between $180 \text{ K} < T < 220 \text{ K}$ for approximately 30 minutes. Samples II, III, IV, and V were synthesized at $T \approx 200$ K using a dry ice–ethanol bath for one hour.

To explore whether the high- T_c fraction could be enhanced, some samples underwent multiple intercalation cycles. This process involved repeated immersions of graphite into Ca–NH₃ solutions, using a manipulator. After each immersion, the sample was lifted above solution (approximately 5-6 cm). The bottom end of the reaction flask was immersed into liquid N₂ to allow the solution being frozen, and excess NH₃ in the lifted samples was pumped out for approximately 10 minutes. Then metal–ammonia solution was melted at $T \approx 200$ K and the intercalation was repeated. Samples subjected to 3 and 10 intercalation cycles showed no significant improvement in the high- T_c fraction.

In addition, we tried to increase the intercalation time by keeping reaction flasks in a Dewar with dry ice up to one week. The final products also did not show enhance of the fraction.

Attempts to intercalate graphite samples with other metal–ammonia solutions, e.g., Sr–NH₃, Na–NH₃, and K–NH₃, were not successful due to extremely high reactivity of these solutions, which often led to spontaneous combustion during sample handling.

Intercalated graphite samples were rapidly transferred to a precooled SQUID magnetometer for magnetization measurements, typically within 2-5 minutes.

The intercalated graphite samples initially exhibit a fascinating gold and dark-blue surface upon delamination, evoking the artistic brilliance of Gustav Klimt’s works. However, over time, these colors faded, and the surface acquired a bronze hue, likely due to intercalant degradation. Bubbling, indicative of ammonia evaporation from the graphite matrix, was also observed (see Supplementary Video). Even after several months at room temperature, the samples retained the characteristic odor of ammonia.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements

D.c. magnetic susceptibility measurements were done in the S700X SQUID magnetometer by Cryogenic Limited. Small pieces of sample (with lateral dimensions of 2.5–4.5 mm and thickness of 1–2 mm) with a total mass of approximately 5-30 mg were covered by anhydrous kerosene or silicone oil and put into a gelatine capsule (an inner diameter of ≈ 4 mm). Samples were predominantly oriented with the carbon layers perpendicular to the applied magnetic field. T_c was determined as the onset of the step-like transitions in the ZFC and FC curves of the temperature dependence of magnetic moment $m(T)$. The geometry-dependent value of the penetration field H_p , at which an applied magnetic field starts to penetrate a sample was determined from the magnetization $m(H)$ measurements as the onset of the evident deviation of the initial virgin $m(H)$ curve from linearity.

The trapped magnetic flux was generated under ZFC and FC conditions. The typical ZFC protocol included cooling of the sample at zero field from $T > T_c$ to the target temperature T_M below T_c . At T_M a magnetic field was applied for approximately 1 hour, then the applied magnetic field was gradually decreased to 0 T. In FC mode the sample was cooled from its normal state at magnetic field to the target temperature T_M below T_c , waiting for approximately 1 hour at T_M , and then an applied magnetic field was gradually decreased to 0 T. After removing an applied magnetic field in both ZFC and FC modes the SQUID magnetometer was allowed to stand for a couple of hours to prevent successive measurements of $m_{\text{trap}}(T)$ from outliers associated with jumps of flux in a superconducting solenoid. An applied magnetic field of magnetization ranged from 16 mT to 2 T. Successive $m_{\text{trap}}(T)$ measurements were performed upon warming and subsequent cooling with a temperature step of 1-3 K. Before each cycle of magnetization, the sample was converted to its normal metal state by warming the sample to $T > T_c$ at zero field and the superconducting magnet of SQUID was degaussed to eliminate the remnant fields. The particular temperature and magnetic field values at magnetization cycle are provided for each sample through the text.

Electrical transport measurements

Four-probe resistance measurements were done on bulk samples of rectangular shape in a configuration with electrodes perpendicular to the carbon layers in samples. The pristine graphite samples were electrically connected using a special holder with gold-plated contact pins in Ar glovebox prior the intercalation reaction. A Si diode temperature sensor was placed close to the sample in quartz ampule filled with He exchange gas at atmospheric pressure. An excitation current from AC resistance bridge (Model 372, Lake Shore) with amplitude of 33 μA – 1 mA and frequency of 13 Hz caused a minimal heating of the sample due to a low scattered heating power about 0.1 nW.

After the intercalation reaction, samples were removed from liquid metal-ammonia solutions by a holder and kept lifted above the liquid for successive $R(T)$ measurements. In particular, sample VI was synthesized by intercalating graphite with Ca–NH₃ solution (Ca in excess, gold color with metallic luster) for 30 minutes. Then sample was lifted from the metal-ammonia solution and pumped out during cooling the sample to approximately 85 K. At 85 K the test tube was filled by He exchange gas and

subsequent electrical measurements were performed. Sample VII was synthesized by intercalation of graphite with diluted calcium ammonia solution ($m(\text{Ca}) = 20$ mg, $V(\text{NH}_3) \approx 3$ mL, blue color) for 15 minutes. Then sample was lifted above the solution and cooled from approximately 200 K to 90 K in He exchange gas, without pumping out. Afterwards several cycles of electrical resistance measurements were performed.

Electrical transport measurements were performed in-situ in the same test-tubes used for the synthesis. For these measurements we used a special holder of samples equipped by four electrical probes and an attached Si diode temperature sensor, which both are movable inside test-tubes. Typically, we used elongated thin samples with a size of approximately $3 \times 1 \times 0.3$ mm³ with four probes made of gold wire with a diameter of 0.07 mm or Pt wire of diameter 0.1 mm. The measurements are tricky as some samples can split during intercalation and temperature cycling. The most stable measurements were done with thin ~ 0.1 mm slabs of graphite. In these measurements apparently both in-plane and normal-to-plane components input in the signal. The in-plane conductivity should be much larger and likely it prevails in the measurements.

It is important to note that the setup for in-situ electrical transport measurements was not optimized for accurate temperature readings directly at the sample. The thermometer was located near (up to 1 cm), but not on, the sample, which may lead to discrepancies between the registered and actual temperatures. This uncertainty was particularly pronounced during cooling due to faster temperature changes compared to the warming cycle. We estimate that the systematic temperature uncertainty can reach 20 K over the temperature range of the observed transitions.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

M.I.E. initiated the research and developed it together with V.S.M and V.K, who contributed equally to the overall research project. The samples were prepared by V.S.M. with contributions from V.K. and M.I.E. The magnetization and electrical transport measurements and their analyses presented in this paper were performed by V.S.M., V.K., and M.I.E. V.S.M. wrote the original draft, V.K., and M.I.E. reviewed and edited the manuscript.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing interests.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Supplementary Figure S1. Magnetization $m(T)$ and $m(H)$ measurements for pristine graphite samples and calcium-ammonia solutions. **a)** ZFC $m(T)$ data for pristine graphite sample (HOPG, blue and magenta circles) and saturated Ca–NH₃ solution in a wide temperature range, showing no anomalies in the temperature range of 230–260 K, in which intercalated samples exhibit transitions. **b)** and **c)** $m(H)$ magnetization data for pristine graphite (HOPG) and saturated Ca–NH₃ solution demonstrating diamagnetic and paramagnetic behavior, respectively. Samples photos are provided.

Supplementary Figure S2. Magnetization $m(T)$ measurements for graphite samples intercalated with calcium-ammonia solutions for longer intercalation time. a) $m(T)$ data for Sample VIII, demonstrating transitions at approximately 230 K. Sample VIII was prepared by intercalating graphite with saturated Ca–NH₃ solutions (excess Ca) at $T \approx 200$ K for one week. **b)** $m(T)$ data for Sample IX, demonstrating transitions at approximately 242 K. Sample IX was prepared by multiple intercalation cycles of graphite with saturated Ca–NH₃ solutions (excess Ca) at $T \approx 200$ K. Sample IX was intercalated three times, each cycle lasted about 30 minutes. Between each intercalation cycle the sample was lifted above the Ca-ammonia solution and pumped out for 10 minutes (see details in Materials and Methods).

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